

ОСОБЕННОСТИ КИШЕЧНОЙ МИКРОБИОТЫ У ДЕТЕЙ С ВРОЖДЕННЫМИ ПОРОКАМИ СЕРДЦА

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Аннотация. Система организма человека рассматривается как симбиотическое соотношение с населяющим его сообществом микроорганизмов. Благодаря развитию доказательной медицины в последние десятилетия появились современные методы, позволяющие изучать спектр микроорганизмов без участия микробиологического культивирования, так как 90% микроорганизмов не культивируются в лабораторных условиях. Современные молекулярно-генетические методы дали возможность обогащать наши понятия о составе микробного пейзажа и их ключевой роли в нашем организме.

Ключевые слова: кишечный микробиом, микробиота кишечника, врожденные пороки сердца у детей, микрофлора кишечника.

Цель работы: анализ особенностей, свойств и роль механизма кишечных микробиот при врожденных пороках сердца (ВПС) у детей по данным зарубежных и отечественных исследований.

Материал и методы: изучены публикации по выбранной теме в базах данных Pubmed, Medline, elibrary.

Результаты и обсуждение: полученные данные включили обзорные понятие о свойствах и составах микробиот при врожденных пороках сердца у детей, позволяют ее изучение не как отдельный орган, а систему организма поддерживающий взаимодействие со всеми системами организма, но и играющую ключевую роль поддержании гомеостаза, резервом адаптационных показателей к меняющимся условиям внутренней и окружающей среды. Определено, что вариабельность микробиоты разнообразная, обычно которая передаётся от матери в утробе и затем после рождение на микробный состав влияют многочисленные факторы, а особенно сердечно-сосудистые патологии и врожденные пороки сердца. Анализ литературных обсуждений дал понятие о роли микробного пейзажа в иммунитете, кишечном барьере при врождённых пороках сердца. Способствуя лучшему пониманию взаимосвязи между ВПС и кишечным микробиомом.

Выводы: микробный пейзаж оказывает непосредственное влияние на все процессы жизнедеятельности человека, таких как пищеварение, адсорбции питательных веществ, активация процессов метаболизма, участвует в процессе защиты кишечника от патогенов, функционирования иммунной системы и в целом поддерживает здоровье организма и кишечника. Все это свидетельствует о необходимости дальнейшего изучения, оценивания и динамического наблюдения детей, имеющих дисфункцию эндотелиального барьера и нарушение кишечной микрофлоры при ВПС у детей, с применением не только общеклинических и инструментальных методов обследования, но и организации эффективного выявления, тактики лечения и реабилитации данной категории детей.

Annotation. The human body system is viewed as a symbiotic relationship with the community of microorganisms inhabiting it. Thanks to the development of evidence-based medicine in recent decades, modern methods have emerged that make it possible to study the spectrum of microorganisms without the participation of microbiological cultivation, since 90%

of microorganisms are not cultivated in laboratory conditions. Modern molecular genetic methods have made it possible to enrich our understanding of the composition of the microbial landscape and their key role in our body.

Key words: intestinal microbiome, intestinal microbiota, congenital heart defects in children, intestinal microflora.

Purpose of the work: analysis of the features, properties and role of the mechanism of intestinal microbiota in congenital heart defects (CHD) in children according to foreign and domestic studies.

Material and methods: publications on the selected topic were studied in the Pubmed, Medline, and elibrary databases.

Results and discussion: the data obtained included a review of the concept of the properties and composition of microbiota in congenital heart defects in children, allowing its study not as a separate organ, but as a body system that supports interaction with all body systems, but also plays a key role in maintaining homeostasis, a reserve of adaptive indicators to changing internal and environmental conditions. It has been determined that the variability of the microbiota is diverse, usually transmitted from the mother in the womb and then after birth, the microbial composition is influenced by numerous factors, especially cardiovascular pathologies and congenital heart defects. Analysis of literary discussions gave an idea of the role of the microbial landscape in immunity, the intestinal barrier in congenital heart defects. Contributing to a better understanding of the relationship between congenital heart disease and the gut microbiome.

Conclusions: the microbial landscape has a direct impact on all human life processes, such as digestion, nutrient absorption, activation of metabolic processes, participates in the process of protecting the intestines from pathogens, the functioning of the immune system, and generally supports the health of the body and intestines. All this indicates the need for further study, assessment and dynamic monitoring of children with endothelial barrier dysfunction and impaired intestinal microflora in children with congenital heart disease, using not only general clinical and instrumental examination methods, but also organizing effective identification, treatment tactics and rehabilitation of this category of children.

Annotatsiya. Inson tanasi tizimi unda yashovchi mikroorganizmlar jamoasi bilan simbiotik munosabatlar sifatida qaraladi. So'nggi o'n yilliklarda dalillarga asoslangan tibbiyotning rivojlanishi tufayli mikroorganizmlarning spektrini mikrobiologik etishtirish ishtirokisiz o'rganish imkonini beradigan zamonaviy usullar paydo bo'ldi, chunki mikroorganizmlarning 90% laboratoriya sharoitida etishtirilmaydi. Zamonaviy molekulyar genetik usullar mikroorganizmlarning tarkibi va ularning tanamizdagi asosiy roli haqidagi tushunchamizni boyitish imkonini berdi.

Kalit so'zlar: ichak mikrobiomi, ichak mikrobioti, bolalarda tug'ma yurak nuqsonlari, ichak mikroflorasi.

Ishning maqsadi: xorijiy va mahalliy tadqiqotlarga ko'ra bolalarda tug'ma yurak nuqsonlari (TYN)da ichak mikrobiotasi mexanizmining xususiyatlari, moxiyatlari va rolini tahlil qilish.

Material va usullar: tanlangan mavzu bo'yicha Pubmed, Medline va elibrary ma'lumotlar bazalaridagi nashrlar o'rganildi.

Natijalar va muhokamalar: olingan ma'lumotlar tug'ma yurak nuqsonlari bor bolalarda ichak mikrobiotalarining xususiyatlari va tarkibi tushunchasini ko'rib chiqishni o'z ichiga oladi, bu uni alohida organ sifatida emas, balki tananing barcha tizimlari bilan o'zaro ta'sirini qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan tana tizimi sifatida o'rganish imkonini berib qolmasdan, balki o'zgaruvchan ichki

va atrof-muhit sharoitlariga moslashish ko'rsatkichlari zaxirasi bo'lgan gomeostazni saqlashda asosiy rol o'ynayshi xam inobatga olingan. Mikrobiotaning o'zgaruvchanligi xilma-xil bo'lib, odatda ona qornida va chakolok tug'ilgandan keyin ichak mikroflorasi tarkibiga ko'plab omillar, xususan, yurak-qon tomir patologiyalari va tug'ma yurak nuqsonlari ta'sir qilishi aniqlangan. Adabiy munozaralar tahlili tug'ma yurak nuqsonlaridagi bor bolalarda ichak mikrobiot manzarasini immunitetdagi va oshqozon ichak bar'er funksiyasidagi o'rni haqida tushuncha berdib, tug'ma yurak kasalligi va ichak mikrobiomi o'rtasidagi ozaro munosabatlarni yaxshiroq tushunishga hissa qo'shadi.

Xulosa: *ichakning mikrobiot manzarasi inson hayotining barcha jarayonlariga, masalan, ovqat hazm qilish, ozuqa moddalarining so'rilishi, metabolik jarayonlarning faollashishiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi, ichaklarni turli patogenlardan himoya qilishda, immunitet tizimining aktivlashida ishtirok etadi va umuman olganda, inson salomatligini qo'llab-quvvatlash bilan tavsiflanadi. Bularning barchasi tug'ma yurak nuqsoni bilan kasallangan bolalarda ichak endotelial disfunksiyasi va ichak mikroflorasi buzilganda nafaqat umumiy klinik va instrumental tekshirish usullaridan foydalangan holda, balki samarali aniqlash, davolash taktikasini va reabilitatsiyani tashkil etishni yanada chukurrok o'rganish, baholash va dinamik monitoring qilish zarurligini ko'rsatadi.*

Congenital malformations (CDM), being the cause of a large number of embryonic and fetal deaths, take first place in the structure of childhood morbidity, disability and mortality in developed countries, which represents a significant medical and social problem [1,2,4]. According to literature data, 303,000 children die annually from developmental defects during the first 4 weeks of life. Developmental disabilities can cause long-term disability, with significant impacts on individuals, their families, health systems and society[3]. Thanks to advances in medicine and changes in the system of organizing care for patients with congenital heart disease, the “critical age of the natural course of the disease” has increased significantly; the problem of studying the prevalence and characteristics of the course of congenital heart disease among children has become urgent. [5,6,7]. Thanks to the intensive development of cardiac surgery, it has become possible to provide effective care for most congenital heart diseases. Currently, the generally accepted tactics for correcting congenital heart disease in childhood. This allows us to minimize the consequences of long-term existence of congenital heart disease, such as pulmonary hypertension, myocardial dysfunction, endocarditis, as well as hematological and neurological complications. Unfortunately, the conditions of other organs and systems remain unstudied. Malnutrition, intestinal infections, repeated courses of antibiotics in children in early childhood conditions can lead to persistent impairment changes in the composition of the microbiota, to the immaturity of the microbiome, reduced and/or increased microbial diversity with numerous negative consequences. Of particular interest is the role host microbiome in the context of susceptibility to different strains of viruses. Especially the state of the microbial landscape and the gastrointestinal system suffers.

There are two concepts: microbiota and microbiome. Microbiota is a set of microorganisms moves that are in a state of symbiosis with the macroorganism. Microbiota distributed on the body human unevenly and forms clusters in places of contact with the environment. Such areas are called biotopes. Biotopes are distinguished skin, oral cavity, respiratory, gastric no-intestinal and genitourinary tracts. The microbiome is a set of genetic material of microorganisms inside the biotope.

Gut microbiota actively influences life processes macroorganism (digestion, metabolism, condition of the gastrointestinal tract, functioning of the immune system, central nervous system (CNS), control of carcinogens. Quality of microbial colonization of the intestine newborn initially depends on the composition mother's intestinal microbiota, consistency placental barrier, contamination with pathogenic microorganisms of amniotic fluid, method of delivery resolution (the newborn is in contact with microbiota of the vaginal canal during natural childbirth, maternal skin, medical staff during surgical childbirth), type of feeding.

There are 4 phases of development of intestinal microbiotanic: in the first phase (from birth to 2 weeks) the predominant give Streptococcus, Escherichia, Lactobacillus, Bifidobacterium, Clostridium, Bacteroides; in the second phase (from 2 weeks before the introduction of complementary foods) - the amount increases Bacteroides; in the third phase (from the introduction of complementary foods until completion of breastfeeding) continued there is an increase in the number of Bacteroides, an increase in anaerobic gram-positive cocci (peptococci and peptostreptococci), the fourth phase begins after stopping breastfeeding with gradual the formation of an "adult" relatively old strong type of gut microbiome approximately by 3 years of age.

The main characteristic of the microbiota is there is a diversity of microorganisms that allows implement many metabolic pathways. There are α - and β -diversity: α -diversity within a community, intestinal microbiota; β -diversity is reported properties of microorganisms that differ in populations, for example, the composition of the intestinal microbiota of residents' cities and villages. The intestinal epitope plays a key role in physiology and maintaining homeostasis of the human body century. Metagenomic studies have allowed understand the composition of the gut microbiome, but more than 99% microbes inhabiting the intestines are not cultivated or are poorly cultivated [3,7,40].

However, congenital heart disease is not a simple anomaly or a simple developmental defect as many believe; This is a very severe disease that affects all body systems. Despite advanced advances in pediatrics and cardiology, which help children with the most dangerous and severe types of congenital heart disease survive, the morbidity rate remains significant, and various questions arise regarding the role of the intestinal microbiome in children with congenital heart disease in the inflammatory process. A more common example of such diseases in most cases is intestinal dysbiosis and barrier dysfunction, which lead to extreme lethal outcomes of this group of diseases [8]. Chronic hypoxia and inflammation associated with heart disease affect the gut microbiome, leading to changes in its abundance, abundance, and composition. In children, mainly after one year of age, the intestinal microbiome performs a lot of functions, which include not only the concept of digestion of nutrients, but also the development and organization of the child's immune system. Often in children with congenital heart disease, the intestinal barrier is disrupted, and through a disrupted intestinal microbiome or its toxic products can enter the general bloodstream, which leads to an inflammatory process. Namely, the determination of the composition of the intestinal microbiota, such as short-chain fatty acids and trimethylamine N-oxide, also play an important role in the diagnosis, treatment and prognosis of congenital heart defects in children [9]. Early identification of disturbances in the intestinal microbiota in pathologies of the cardiovascular system and blood circulation in sick children with congenital heart defects plays a key role in determining the prognosis of their life[10].

The intestinal microbiota is considered the main link in maintaining health and regulating homeostasis in general [11,12,13,14], and its dysfunction, i.e. Failure of regulation (the so-called intestinal dysbiosis) leads to a critical condition causing multiple organ disorders in pediatrics [16,17,18] and in cardiac surgery [16,17,18] 18,19, 20]. It is known that with intestinal dysbiosis, a restructuring and imbalance of the normal intestinal microflora occurs. This imbalance has a basis in inflammatory bowel disease, autoimmune disorders and hypoxia[17 , 18 , 19, 20 , 21].

Today, the population of sick children with combined developmental defects is growing in connection with disruption of the intestinal microflora due to hypoxia and numerous use of medications, but the underlying disease is often treated as a disorder of the cardiovascular system, and patients' questions about specific disrupted gut microbiota continues to grow. Still, today the issue of microbiota disturbance in sick children with congenital heart disease remains relevant due to many stressful situations, ignorance of the concept of the disease by parents and medical personnel, including pathological blood flow to the intestines, hypoxemia, poor appetite, impaired nutritional factors and a decrease in cardiac output from the heart. valvular regurgitation and/or collateral cardiac shunts and this group remains at risk of developing dysbiosis, intestinal dysbiosis and intestinal epithelial barrier dysfunction (EBD) [22].

In today's modern society of doctors, many scientists claim that dysbiosis is diagnosed in 70% of patients with congenital heart defects [23,24,25]. However, the effect of probiotics and synbiotics in correcting dysbiosis or treating intestinalepithelial barrier dysfunction in patients with congenital heart disease has not been well studied [26,27].

As is known, congenital heart disease leads to decreased systemic blood flow and/or intestinal hypoxemia. This is an important key factor in the development of dysbiosis, changes in the normal intestinal flora, a decrease in the number of beneficial bacteria, which contributes to an increase in the number of pro-inflammatory bacteria. And they, in turn, activate the production of cytokine-like molecules, pathological metabolites and toxins. And these pathological products activate intestinal barrier dysfunction, completely disrupting the integrity of cells and increasing the flow of toxins and cytokines from the systemic circulation. In addition, these pathological metabolites activate an increase in TMAO, which leads to endothelial dysfunction, an increased risk of thrombosis, changes in cardiac contractility and ultimately fibrosis of cardiac tissue. Dysbiosis also activates a decrease in the concentration of secondary bile acids in interaction with a decrease in cardiac inotropy and an increase in the level of circulating cytokines. This mechanism activates a decrease in the concentration of short-chain fatty acids such as butyrate, which leads to decreased vascular tone and increased intestinal inflammation, leading to leaky gut syndrome in patients. Further accumulation of pathological products and harmful toxins activates a decrease in nitric oxide, which leads to pulmonary vasoconstriction and promotes the progressive growth of pro-inflammatory bacteria [34,35].

From clinical cases, it is known that in children with congenital heart defects, vasoconstriction associated with hypoxemia is more common, resulting in impaired blood flow in the intestines. The latter, in turn, activates inflammation, causing changes in the intestinal microbiota. Such unambiguous changes are also observed with reduced systemic blood flow[28]. A healthy intestinal barrier is a powerful defense against intestinal pathogens, various inflammatory agents and exo- and endotoxins produced by intestinal bacteria, however intestinal hypoxia creates favorable conditions for dysbiosis and the height of these events. High level of damage to the gastrointestinal tract in the form of dysbiosis intestines in most young children with congenital heart defects is probably also associated with frequent use antibiotic therapy. Presence

of gastrointestinal syndrome, microbiological disorders landscape of the intestines and lower parts of the digestive tract are factors complicating the course of congenital heart defects in children, which makes timely surgical treatment difficult [31]. Increased contamination of one or another area of the gastrointestinal tract with opportunistic microflora reduces its bactericidal properties and can serve as an indicator of reduction immunological reactivity of the macroorganism. Frequent use of antibiotic therapy with standard treatment in children with congenital heart disease leads to damage to the gastrointestinal tract in the form of dysbiosis and intestinal dysbiosis, causing the symptom of “leaky gut”. This facilitates the entry of viruses into the body through surfaces and mucous membranes, which traditionally should be destroyed by commensal microbes. This leads to imbalance of the intestinal microflora with the formation of dysbacteriosis in children with congenital heart defects of viral etiology, but unfortunately we try to treat with antiviral drugs and correction of congenital heart disease, forgetting about the intestinal flora. The intestinal landscape of the digestive tract is the main factor that develops complications and worsens the prognosis congenital heart defects in children, which makes it timely surgical treatment is difficult [31,32,33]. Contaminated, hypoxemic, impaired protective barrier intestine becomes a victim for microbes, as a result of which both the immune system and the hemostasis of the macroorganism suffer [22,28,30,31].

Methods of molecular genetic sequencing latest generation (high-performance metagenomic 16,S rRNA sequencing and complete nongenomic sequencing) allowed hundreds of times speed up the process of determining nucleotide sequences sequences of DNA and RNA, map dozens of thousands of microorganisms - bacteria, viruses, fungi beans, protozoa that live in the human body, especially in the oral cavity[29]. The use of a selective method for determining the intestinal landscape can prevent various complications encountered after surgery in children with congenital heart disease. Because of which children cannot gain sufficient weight for surgical procedures and even after surgery due to impaired intestinal perfusion

Thus, studying the gut microbiome allows develop new medical technologies. This concerns not only the general principles of disease treatment, but also the transition to personalized medicine based on the achievements of pharmacomicrobiomics. Intestinal landscape is an important area of focus in sick children with congenital heart disease and is associated with intestinal barrier dysfunction and systemic inflammation. Larger studies assessing the microbiome in this patient population are needed to better understand how changes in the microbiota impact congenital heart disease outcomes. Correction of dysbiotic disorders is necessary depending on the severity and clinical manifestations - balanced nutritional support, pro- or prebiotics,enzyme preparations, bacteriophages, enterosorbents.

LITERATURE

1. Юдина Ю.В., Корсунский А.А., Аминова А.И., Абдуллаева Г.Д., Продеус А.П. Микробиота кишечника как отдельная система организма Доказательная гастроэнтерология. 2019;8(4): 36-43с.
2. Cho, I.; Blaser, M.J. The people microbiome: At the interface of health *Jetere* 2012, №13, 260–270с.
3. Mashara A.M., Tugani F. The gut flora as a big organ. *EMBO Rep.* 2006, №7, 688–693с.
4. Белозеров Ю. М. Детская кардиология : МЕДпресс-информ, 2004. 321-597с.

5. Гильбоа С., Нембхард С.Дж., Фикслер В.Н., Корреа Д.Э. А. Смертность от врожденных пороков сердца среди детей и взрослых в США, 1999–2006 гг. Кровообращение. 2010;122: 54–63с.
6. Николаева И.В., Андреева Ш.К. Царегородцев А.Д., Шайхиева Г.С. Формирование кишечной микробиоты ребенка и младенца и факторы, влияющие на этот процесс. Российский вестник перинатологии и педиатрии 2018; 63(3): 13–18с.
7. Лопес С. и др. Смертность от критических врожденных пороков сердца и связанные с ними факторы риска у новорожденных. Когортное исследование. Арк Брас Кардиол. 2018;111: 66–73с.
8. Прал Лаис П., Хосе Л. Фачи, Ренан О. Корреа, Марко Колонна и Марко А.Р. Виноло 2021г. «Гипоксия и HIF-1 как ключевые регуляторы микробиоты кишечника и взаимодействия с хозяином». Тенденции в иммунологии №42: 604 – 621с.
9. Хавкин А. И. Микрофлора пищеварительного тракта / А. И. Хавкин. Фонд социальной педиатрии, 2006. – 416 с.
10. S. Böthig, J. Knappe, K. H. Günther Epidemiology and prevention of cardiac insufficiency Dtsch Gesundheitsw 2020 №13 Sep 1;27-36с.
11. Kamada N, Nunez G., Figoni F.R. Control of pathogens and pathobionts by the gut microbiota. Nat Immunol. 2013;14: 90-104с.
12. Plummer NT. Part 4: The people Gut Microbiome in Health and Disease. Integr Med (Encinitas). 2014;13с.
13. Wang H, Wei C-X, Y. Biotechnology Biotechnological Equipment. 2018; 14-15с.
14. Машурина Л.А., Григорьев К.И., Борзакова С.Н. Микробиота человека: как новая научная тартета, что меняет медицинскую практику. Клиническая гастроэнтерология 2019; 161(1): 55–63с.
15. Юдина Ю.В., Яколавская А.А., Аминова А.И., Абдуллаева Г.Д., Продеус А.П. Микробиота кишечника как отдельная система организма. Доказательная гастроэнтерология 2019; 8(4–5): 36–43с.
16. Хоттир Н, et al. Marked Changes in Gut Microbiota in Cardio-Surgical Intensive Care Patients: A Longitudinal Cohort Study. 2021;22-37с.
17. Tutirs S, et al. Clinical Parameters and Gut Microbiome Changes Before and After Surgery in Thoracic Aortic Dissection in Patients with Gastrointestinal Complications. Sci Rep. 2017;15-28с.
18. Songol W, et al. Clinical Multi-Omics Study on the Gut Microbiota in Critically Ill Patients After Cardiovascular Surgery Combined With Cardiopulmonary Bypass With or Without Sepsis (MUL-GM-CSCPВ Study): A Prospective Study Protocol. Front Med (Lausanne). 2020; 55-64с.
19. Cenit M.C, Sanz Y., Codoner-Franch P. Influence of gut microbiota on neuropsychiatric disorders. World J Gastroenterol. 2017 86–98с.
20. Agzamova Sh.A., Babadjanova F.R., Khasanova G.M. Prevalence and Clinical Characteristics of Congenital Heart Diseases in children of Khorezm region of The Republic of Uzbekistan. Journal of Advanced Medical and Dental Sciences Research 2021;9(4):63-67с
21. Agzamova Sh.A., Babadjanova F.R., Tashenova G.T. Morphometric Determinants of Myocardial Dysfunction in Children with Congenital Heart Defects in the Postoperative Period. Telematique, 2023/6/1;1446-1457с.

22. Agzamova Sh.A., Babadjanova F.R., Risk of cephalgic complications according to ultra sound duplex scanning of carotid artery in children with CHD within postoperative period. Science and innovation №2.D5 27-33с.
23. Patterget S, et al Gastrointestinal microbiota diversity and clinical outcomes in congenital heart disease. 2020 Critical Care Medicine 48(1):68с.
24. Salomon J, Price A, Manithody C, Jain A, Effect of cardiopulmonary, bypass on the pediatric intestinal microbiome. 2021 Apr; 6(4): 311–327с.
25. Junyue Xing, Yongquan Ying, Chenxi Mao, Yiwei Liu, Tingting Wang, Qian Zhao, Xiaoling Zhang, Fuxia Yan & Hao Zhang Hypoxia induces senescence of bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells via altered gut microbiota. Nature Communications volume 9, Article number: 2020 (2018)1-10с.
26. Хуан, Юань, Вэньлун Лу, Мин Цзэн, Сяюэ Ху, Чжаньхао Су, Ивэй Лю, Цзэй Лю и др. «Картирование микробиома кишечника в раннем возрасте у новорожденных с критическим врожденным пороком сердца: выводы и последствия мультиомики для метаболического и иммунологического здоровья хозяина». Микробиом 10,2022 / 245-255 с.
27. Прал, Лаис П. , Хосе Л. Фачи , Ренан О. Корреа , Марко Колонна и Марко А.Р. Виноло «Гипоксия и HIF-1 как ключевые регуляторы микробиоты кишечника и взаимодействия с хозяином». Тенденции в иммунологии 2021/ 604 – 621с.
28. Ся, Сюн , Цзянцзинь Ни , Шэннань Инь , Чжипен Ян , Хайни Цзян , Чао Ван , Цзянь Пэн , Хункуй Вэй и Синьюй Ван .« Повышенная системная и кишечная воспалительная реакция связана с нарушением микробиома кишечника после сердечно-сосудистой хирургии». Границы микробиологии 2021г, 421-507с.
29. Reuter JA, Spacek DV, Snyder MP. High-throughput sequencing technologies. Mol Cell. 2015 May 21;58(4): 86-97с.
30. Zeitoni NE, Chotikatum S, von Kockritz-Blickwede M, Naim HY. The impact of hypoxia on intestinal epithelial cell functions: consequences for invasion by bacterial pathogens. Mol Cell Pediatr. 2016;3:14. 26-65с.
31. Яковлева Л. В., Сафиуллина А. Р., Раянова Р. Р.. Особенности состояния пищеварительного тракта у детей с врожденными септальными пороками сердца. Оренбургский медицинский вестник Том 5№2, 32-46с.;
32. Cremerintto J, et al. Systemic inflammatory response syndrome after cardiac operations. The Annals of Thoracic Surgery. 1996;61:14–20с.
33. Sohpal R., Lau J.T., Yuan Y., Leontiadis G.I., Tse F., Surette M., Moayyedi P. Gut Microbiota in Patients With Irritable Bowel Syndrome. A Systematic Review. Gastroenterology 2019; 157(1): 97–108с.
34. Mshunint G., Lopetuso L.R., Gibiino G., Binda C., Gasbarrini A, Proteobacteria: Common Factor in Human Diseases. Biomed Res Int 2017, (2017).46-85с.
35. Jeffrey Salomon, MD,a,b,* Aaron Ericsson, DVM, PhD,c Amber Price, “ Dysbiosis and Intestinal Barrier Dysfunction in Pediatric Congenital Heart Disease Is Exacerbated Following Cardiopulmonary Bypass” JACC Basic Transl Sci. 2021 Apr; 6(4): 311–327с.